

THE NEED TO FORM A SENSE OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AMONG THE OWNERS.

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Social responsibility means that owners are aware of their role and impact on society and the environment. This includes taking steps to address negative impact and create positive change in society. Realizing their social responsibility, owners can contribute to social programs, charity, environmental protection and other socially important initiatives. It helps to strengthen social capital and recognition of owners in society.

The role of a sense of social responsibility is important in the full development of an individual in society. It is an urgent issue to analyze the formation of this feeling in the stratum of owners from a socio-philosophical point of view and to harmonize it with the feeling of national identity.

According to the researcher I. Ergashev, "Responsibility is a comprehensive concept, which as a philosophical category means the realization of human actions in social reality in a state of awareness. In some literature, the following types of it are noted separately: social responsibility, moral responsibility, material responsibility, physical responsibility, spiritual responsibility, natural responsibility"¹.

As for the concept of social responsibility, it is a concept that indicates the responsibility of a person or organization to be responsible for their actions and the impact on society as a whole. It is necessary to approach the concept of social responsibility with real relations, in which it is necessary to proceed from the interdependence of rights and obligations, and it is necessary to take into account what place an individual or a group of people will have in the process of social relations. The greater the social functions and real possibilities of individuals, the higher their level of responsibility.

Many researchers have expressed their thoughts and opinions on the issue of social responsibility. One of the important philosophical theories related to social responsibility is the theory of deontology ethics developed by Immanuel Kant. He stated that people should follow responsibility and obligations in their

¹ Эргашев.И. "Шахс маънавий камолотида эркинлик ва ижтимоий масъулият уйғунлиги" Фалсафа доктори (PhD) даражасини олиш учун ёзилган диссертацияси. – Тошкент: 2011. – 21- б

actions. Therefore, social responsibility requires an individual or organization to fulfill their obligations and fulfill them within the framework of social norms and values.

I.M. Parmonova stated that "social responsibility is understood as a moral factor that determines the activity and rational activity of a person in social relations"². According to our opinion, we interpret this given definition as follows. Social responsibility refers to behavior that takes into account the impact of one's actions on society and the people around him. This means that an individual must consider his social responsibility and the consequences of his actions for society as a whole.

Social responsibility is first of all formed in a person as a personal quality and has its influence on different layers of society. A special sense of social responsibility is formed, including among the owners. By the social responsibility of the property owners, we mean their responsibility to society and the state through their property.

Today, modern society requires owners to be socially responsible towards individuals. In this regard, researcher I. Ledyaykina writes: "property imposes on a person not only the rights to use the property, but also the responsibility, the owner is required not to violate the property rights and freedoms of other owners and ordinary citizens in the process of using his property"³

As a result of our philosophical-theoretical analysis of the issue of social responsibility formation among the owners, we came to the following conclusions.

First, owners need to exemplify leadership behavior at a high level.

Second, if the company introduces a sense of social responsibility in its values and principles, it can influence the mentality of the owners and make them more oriented towards social issues.

Third, the realization that social responsibility can lead to long-term business sustainability and enhance business reputation can encourage investors to invest in social programs and initiatives.

Fourth, the presence of strict norms and regulations in the field of social responsibility can be an incentive for owners to take appropriate measures and invest in social and environmental initiatives.

² Пармонова.И.М. Социальная ответственность как система//Известия СПбГЭТУ.Сер. "Гуманитарные и социальное-экономические науки", 2000. Т.Вып. 1.-С.16.

³ Ледяйкина И. "Собственность как совокупность прав,и социальной ответственности".- Экономика образования, 2009,74 с.

Fifth, media and public opinion coverage of social issues can influence owners to actively support social programs and demonstrate responsible behavior.

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